

STUDIES ON METAL FERROCYANIDES. PART II. VOLUMETRIC DETERMINATION OF TRIVALENT CERIUM BY FERROCYANIDE

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Precipitation of $CeKFe(CN)_6$ from a solution of cerous chloride with potassium ferrocyanide of varying concentrations has been carried out for the determination of Ce^{III} . The excess ferrocyanide is titrated with standard ceric sulphate and from the changed ferrocyanide the amount of Ce^{III} calculated. This new volumetric procedure has been found to provide sufficiently accurate results under the conditions specified.

The formation of cerium-ferrocyanide complexes of the composition $CeKFe(CN)_6$ in the gravimetric determination of trivalent cerium, involving the precipitation of $CeKFe(CN)_6 \cdot 4H_2O$ and subsequent weighing of the precipitate, has been reported by Spacu and others (Spacu, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1936, 104, 119; Atanasiu, *ibid.*, 1936, 106, 422; Schenijakin and Volkova, *J. Gen. Chem. USSR.*, 1937, 17, 1328, 1332). In the present paper the above procedure of Spacu has been extended to the determination of Ce^{III} by a volumetric method involving the formation of $CeKFe(CN)_6$ from a solution of cerous chloride, with a known excess of ferrocyanide and indirect estimation of the excess ferrocyanide by standard ceric sulphate.

EXPERIMENTAL

A stock solution of $CeCl_3$ was prepared by dissolving a pure Merck sample of cerous chloride in water. The weight of Ce in this solution was determined by precipitation as cerous oxalate, subsequent ignition to ceric oxide and weighing as CeO_2 . Potassium ferrocyanide solutions of a pure Merck sample of different concentrations, varying from 1 to 4%, were prepared and the exact concentration determined by titrations with standard ceric sulphate.

A known quantity of cerous chloride solution was pipetted into a beaker to which was added a known excess of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution, and kept aside overnight with frequent shaking. Arrangement for filtration was made using filter cones of Whatman No. 50, provided with suction arrangements. The excess of ferrocyanide was filtered off slowly, then the precipitate was transferred and washed well with water till all ferrocyanide was washed off in the filtrate. To the above filtrate 20 c.c. of 4.5N- H_2SO_4 was added, and a drop of phenanthroline-ferrous complex as indicator, and titrated against standard ceric sulphate solution to the end-point. A preliminary titration of a known quantity of ferrocyanide was carried out against standard ceric sulphate. From the titre values, the amount of ferrocyanide reacting was calculated.

Different concentrations of the ferrocyanide varying from 1 to 4% solution were tried and the accuracy of the method for different concentrations of cerium was worked out. For the titration relationship the precipitate appears to have the composition $CeKFe(CN)_6$ for the different concentrations of ferrocyanide studied. Typical sets of results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Vol. of $CeCl_3$.	Conc. of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$.	Wt. of Ce by ferrocyanide.	Wt. of Ce by cerous oxalate.	Diff.
5 c.c.	25 c.c. of 1% soln.	0.01503 g.	0.01498 g.	0.00005
"	" 2	"	"	"
"	" 4	"	"	"
10	25 of 1	0.03006	0.01996	0.00010
"	" 2	"	"	"
"	" 4	"	"	"
12	25 of 2	0.03582	0.03595	0.00013
"	" 4	"	"	"
14	25 of 2	0.04163	0.04194	0.00031
"	" 4	"	"	"
15	25 of 1	0.04513	0.04494	0.00019
"	" 2	"	"	"
20	50 of 1	0.06017	0.05992	0.00025
"	25 of 2	0.05954	"	0.00038
"	25 of 4	0.05954	"	0.00038
25	50 of 1	0.07469	0.07498	0.00029
"	25 of 2	0.07406	"	0.00092
"	25 of 4	0.07406	"	0.00092
30	50 of 1	0.08828	0.08988	0.00160
"	25 of 2	"	"	"
"	25 of 4	"	"	"

The complex formation observed in this case is essentially supported by the conclusions of Spacu and others (*loc. cit.*).

In addition to the accuracy of the method, the importance of a volumetric method of determination of Ce^{III} with ferrocyanide, involving indirect titration of the ferrocyanide with ceric sulphate, *i.e.* Ce^{IV} , is of high value. Again the volumetric procedure involves less complications and the error is less as compared to gravimetric procedures.

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